

**IMPACT OF SOCIAL MEDIA AND SOCIAL SUPPORT ON THE SOCIAL
ADJUSTMENT OF ADOLESCENT WITH VISUAL IMPAIRMENT IN
IBADAN OYO STATE**

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ABSTRACT

This paper examines the impact of social media and social support on social adjustment of adolescents with visual impairment in Oyo state. Purpose of the study is to identifying the relationship between social media and social support on social adjustment of adolescents with visual impairment; investigate the joint contributions of the social media and social support to social adjustment of adolescents with visual impairment and the relative contributions of social media and social support to social adjustment of adolescents with visual impairment. The study adopts a survey research design, the sample for the study comprises of 70 respondents who were adolescent with visual impairment. Pearson's Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) and multiple regression was used in analyzing data collected from the field. From the study, the results show that social media and social support has significance relationship with social adjustment, also, there is joint contributions of social media and social support to social adjustment and the relative contributions of social media and social support to social adjustment of adolescents with visual impairment was also significant. The study recommends that adolescent with visual impairment needs social media to be able to support themselves and the parents as well as the teachers should give the necessary support to be able to adjust fully to the community life styles and changes.

Keywords: Social media, social support, social adjustment, Adolescent, Visual impairment.

INTRODUCTION

Adolescent is a period of dependency and preparation to adulthood, it has since been reinforced through more recent social changes, including economic restructuring and changing cultural norms about parenting, this is to say that the adolescent stage entails series of changes in all aspects of a child it centers on all what the child will come across with within the society (Golding and Katz 2008)

The adolescent period is a period of rapid change, which are usually dramatically crystalised in the flood of hormonal activities and rapid physiological development that constitutes puberty (Susan 2008) in the years following, puberty, adolescent are faced with the task of establishing their own identity separated from their parents , they are left with the decision to choose on their own or to do things their way, (Knoger 2007), however, those choices or behavior made may lead them into risky behaviors such as smoking, drinking, use of drugs, sexual activities and lots more, it is a period of development and exploitation therefore, they practice things they see and hear themselves as a child grows, into puberty, hormones get increase so rapidly in regions that controls sensational seeking which encourages behaviour that bring about some emotional or sensational rewards (Steriberg, 2008) to Cawanagh (2004) and Haynie (2003) they both attested that they are adult-like physically and as a result, may engage in actions or put themselves in situations that are ahead of their emotional or cognitive capacities, with this they need someone to guide and put them through, what most this adolescent need most times is support and encouragement to make them choose the right thing in life , they shouldn't be neglected to do things on their own , some of them pass through distress and other socio-emotional difficulties the society is responsible to nurture and guide each child, social support is the pro-social behaviors or attitude that individual receive from their family and social environment with the aim of enhancing social functioning with social interactions (Nolte, 1994).

The ability of an individual with visual impairment to adjust to situations, conditions or challenges that may arise as a result of their impairment depends on their level of acceptability, recognition and accommodation by their parents, family, peers and society. Among the invigorating factors that assist the persons with visual impairment to have good interpersonal relationship leads to good psychological adjustment include the active involvement of their parents in their daily exercise supported by their level of emotional intelligence and self-concept (Abodunrin and Komolafe, 2017).

Social support is positively related to social skills since it allows the individual to seek and maintain social support (Elliot, McGregor 2001) the development of the sense of belonging and acceptance in the social environment for

the provision of instruments and emotional support from teachers and peers (Pavri and Monda-Amaya 2001) despite the fact that the importance of social support for those children requiring additional support or for those who are at risk for developing psycho-social difficulties have been widely acknowledged (Tilly 2008) indeed social support can help adolescent cope and in time of distress, it also influences whether it can have a long term effect or in other areas of life, including education.

People of all ages have embraced technology and social media to stay in touch with family and friends to learn about the latest news and stay connected with what happens throughout the world, visual impairment is a condition of reduced visual performance that cannot be remedied by refractive correction furthermore, those individuals are sometimes capable of enhancing their abilities to accomplish visual task with the use of compensatory low vision or environmental adjustment, having a disability can limit participation in daily living activities and reduces participation and social activities in particular young people with visual impairment, faces challenges with establishing and maintaining relationship pertaining to group leisure and physical activities including, building, successful school work career, people need to adapt and communicate, mobile communication technology is an essential part of life of an adolescent, nowadays those with visual impairment are not exempted (Adoti, 2006).

Social media is the digital tool that allows users to quickly create and share content with the public on virtual communities and network, it also serve as a means of communication tool to learn, it is a bidirectional process; it refers to any digital platform, system, website or app. The web is becoming more visual impaired-friendly by the day, for example, AudioBoo is an audio-focused network that is focused on helping visually impaired connect with others via audio. Visual-impairment may affect the lives of adolescents and adults although the effects of visual-impairment on adolescents may be taken for granted as they account for less than half the population affected by visual impairment. Affected children and adolescents may endure a lifetime of vision-related difficulties that may affect their education, social interactions and possible future employment. It is generally acknowledged that adolescents with disabilities often encounter additional adversities, disadvantages and difficulties during their development and experience exclusion from age-appropriate activities (Hart, 2014).

Social adjustment has been found to be predictive for depression and suicide attempt, especially in this present life events, involving personal loss, like separation, divorce or of death in the family which can lead to depressive symptoms whereas stressful like events involving a threat (De Beurs, Kendler and Heim 2007). Jain (2010) asserts that social adjustment is psychological process which is concerned with the effort made by an individual to cope with standards and values.

Neihart (2007) adjustment refers to the process of responding to the environmental demands and students who positively adjust to new circumstances are able to cope effectively with the demands of life, it is a way or form of satisfying relationship with other people and emotional adjustment, it means users to include a wide variety of characteristics such as social self-concept, social maturity, peer acceptance, friendship, engagement, in organization and family relations. (Rogers, 2015) social adjustment is the adjustment in social institutions and it can be viewed from two main points. The first view is that social adjustment is an achievement, that is, a person can perform his duties in different social circumstances or activities, while the other view sees social adjustment as a process which is of social importance to psychologists, teachers and parents, the process of social adjustment from birth of a child and it continues till death, thus social adjustment is reactions to the demands and pressures of social environment imposed upon the individual socially, adjustment becomes more frustrated due to the fact that view of the members of the society who associate themselves with the student with visual impairment withdrew (Abodunrin, Assam and Abodunrin 2021).

The visually impaired are the group of people characterized by inefficiency in the organ of sight which hinders individual capability in performing various functions that requires the use of sight (Abodunrin and Abodunrin, 2020). Visual impairment may limit social interactions and have a negative impact on individual's socio-emotional development. They tend to spend most of their time in solitary and parallel play, and do not usually engage in imaginative play or social interactions with their sighted mates (McGaha and Farran, 2001). This may be due to the limitation they face in perceiving both visual cues and other non-verbal movements (Celeste, 2006). There is also evidence that the adolescent with visual-impairment faces problems which may stem from a number of factors such as neurological impairments associated with their vision, limited participation in leisure time activities, increased dependency on others and increased parental control (Augustad, 2017). Thus, this research work takes a look into social media and social support on social adjustment of adolescents with visual impairment in Ibadan.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study is to:

- i. Identify the relationship between the independent variable (social media and social support) and the dependent variable (social adjustment) of adolescents with visual impairment.
- ii. Examine the joint contribution of the independent variable (social media and social support) to the dependent variable (social adjustment) of adolescents with visual impairment.

- iii. Investigate the relative contribution of the independent variable (social media and social support) to the dependent variable (social adjustment) of adolescents with visual impairment.

Research Questions

The following research questions serve as guide to this study:

- i. What is the relationship between the independent variable (social media and social support) and the dependent variable (social adjustment) of adolescents with visual impairment?
- ii. What is the joint contribution of the independent variable (social media and social support) to the dependent variable (social adjustment)?
- iii. What is the relative contribution of the independent variable (social media and social support) to the dependent variable (social adjustment) of adolescents with visual impairment?

Research Setting

Oyo State is an inland state in South-Western Nigeria. Its capital is Ibadan, the third most populous city in the country and formerly the second most populous city in Africa. The state borders Kwara State to the North, to the East by Osun state, and to the South-West by Ogun State and the Republic of Benin. Its total population is about 5,580.894 as at 2006 population census.

Education for children with disability in Nigeria

Educational programme for children with disability are in three forms:

1. Special school: in this educational settings, children with disability are enrolled in a special school for children with disability. This special school are of two types. These are residential special school and special day school. Residential special school are institution where-by children with disability apart from receiving their school education, also live in. there is generally a residential quarters attached to the school while the special day school, children with disability are enrolled in a special school. Unlike residential school, the children return home after school hours to their various own homes.
2. Integrated school or main streaming educational programme: this is where children with disability are placed in a regular school with their sighted counterparts and they both receive instructions together in a class under the same teachers, with additional aids to the children with disability by specialist in the resource room.
3. Inclusive education; this kind of educational setting is available in Nigeria. It is designed to meet the educational needs of children with disability. At this settings, children with disability received instructions under regular

teachers supported by specially trained teachers and other personnel in a classroom with their non-disabled counterpart.

METHODOLOGY

The research design adopted for this study is the descriptive survey. The population of this study comprises of all adolescents with visual impairment in Oyo State. The sample of the study consist of 70 adolescents, with visual impairment drawn from tertiary institutions in Oyo State, purposive sampling technique was used to select samples for the study including total blind and low vision, this was done because of the unique attributes of the respondent and for equal evidence of representation. The Data collected was analyzed using descriptive statistics of frequency counts and mean for the demographic information for the respondent and the inferential statistics of Pearson product movement correlation, (PPMC) to answer research questions.

RESULTS

Demographic distribution of respondents

Table 1: Frequency distribution of respondents by gender

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	40	57.1
Female	30	42.9
Total	70	100.0

Table 1 shows that 40(57.1%) adolescents are male, and their female counterparts are 30(42.9%)

Table 2: Frequency distribution of respondents by degree of visual loss

Degree of visual loss	Frequency	Percentage
Totally blind	33	47.1
Low vision	37	52.9
Total	70	100.0

Table 2 shows that 33(47.1%) adolescents are totally blind, and 37(52.9%) had low vision.

Table 3 Frequency distribution of respondents by age

Age	Frequency	Percentage
12-16 years	34	48.6
17-18 years	8	11.4
19-23 years	28	40.0
Total	70	100.0

Table 3 shows that 34(48.6%) adolescents are between 12-16 years of age, 8(11.4%) are between 17-18 years, and 28(40.0%) are between 19-23 years of age.

Table 4: Frequency distribution of respondents by onset of impairment

Onset of impairment	Frequency	Percentage
Congenital	3	4.3
Acquired	67	95.7
Total	70	100.0

Table 4 shows that 3(4.3%) adolescents had congenital onset of impairment, and 67(95.7%) had acquired onset of impairment in the study.

Answering of research questions

Research question one:

What are the relationship between the independent variables (Social media and Social support) and the dependent variable (Social adjustment) of adolescents with visual impairment?

Table 5 Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) showing the relationship between Social media and Social support, and Social adjustment of adolescents with visual impairment

	Social adjustment	Social media	Social support
Social adjustment	1		
Social media	.400* (.001)	1	
Social support	.366* (.002)	.346* (.003)	1
Mean (\bar{x})	18.0457	13.8000	24.6429
S.D	3.89925	7.87327	3.24835

* Sig. at 0.05 level

Table 5 shows that there is a significant relationship between social adjustment of adolescents with visual impairment and social media ($r = .400$, $p(.000) < .05$), and Social support ($r = .366$, $p(.000) < .05$), improve social media and social support enhanced social adjustment of adolescents with visual impairment in the study.

Research question two:

What are the joint contribution of the independent variable (Social media and Social support) to the dependent variable (Social adjustment) of adolescents with visual impairment?

Table 6 Summary of Regression analysis showing the joint effect of social media and social support on social adjustment of adolescents with visual impairment

R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate			
.671	.450	.433	2.93570			
A N O V A						
Model	Sum of Squares	DF	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Remark
Regression	471.657	2	235.828	27.364	.001	Sig.
Residual	577.429	67	8.618			
Total	1049.086	69				

Table 6 shows the joint effect of social media and social support on social adjustment. The table also shows a coefficient of multiple correlation $R = .671$ and a multiple R^2 of .450. This means that 45.0% of the variance was accounted for by the two predictor variables when taken together. The significance of the composite contribution was tested at $\alpha = 0.05$. The table also shows that the analysis of variance for the regression yielded F-ratio of 27.364 (significant at 0.05 level). This implies that the joint contribution of the independent variables to the dependent variable was significant and that other variables not included in this model may have accounted for the remaining variance.

Research question three: What are the relative contribution of the independent variable (Social media and Social support) to the dependent variable (Social adjustment) of adolescents with visual impairment?

Table 7. Summary of regression analysis showing the relative contribution of social media and social support on social adjustment of adolescents with visual impairment

Model	Unstandardized Coefficient		Standardized Coefficient	t	Sig. p
	B	Std. Error	Beta Contribution		
(Constant)	-3.013	3.168		-.951	.345
Social media	.296	.048	.599	6.196	.000
Social support	.689	.116	.574	5.937	.000

Table 8 Measures of social media as a correlate of social adjustment of adolescents with visual impairment

s/n	Social media	Never	Rarely	Sometimes	Pretty often	A lot	\bar{x}	S.D
1	Facebook	5 7.1%	5 7.1%	14 20.0%	15 21.4%	31 44.3%	2.89	1.257
2	Instagram	43 61.4%	7 10.0%	6 8.6%	11 15.7%	3 4.3%	0.91	1.316
3	Twitter	50 71.4%	6 8.6%	7 10.0%	4 5.7%	3 4.3%	0.63	1.144
4	Snapchat	59 84.3%	3 4.3%	3 4.3%	4 5.7%	1 1.4%	0.36	0.917
5	Tumblr	57 81.4%	5 7.1%	4 5.7%	3 4.3%	1 1.4%	0.37	0.887
6	Vine	42 60.0%	9 12.9%	9 12.9%	8 11.4%	2 2.9%	0.84	1.199
7	YouTube	26 37.1%	8 11.4%	14 20.0%	12 17.1%	10 14.3%	1.60	1.488
8	Pinterest	38 54.3%	6 8.6%	9 12.9%	10 14.3%	7 10.0%	1.17	1.464
9	Reddit	43 61.4%	12 17.1%	5 7.1%	6 8.6%	4 5.7%	0.80	1.235
10	LinkedIn	38 54.3%	6 8.6%	6 8.6%	14 20.0%	6 8.6%	1.20	1.480
11	Google	36 51.4%	8 11.4%	10 14.3%	7 10.0%	9 12.9%	1.21	1.483
12	Email	45 64.3%	7 10.0%	4 5.7%	6 8.6%	8 11.4%	0.93	1.448
13	WhatsApp	51 72.9%	1 1.4%	4 5.7%	3 4.3%	11 15.7%	0.89	1.547

Weighted Mean= 1.06

Table 7 shows that the relative contribution of the independent variables to the dependent variable, expressed as beta weights, viz: Social media ($\beta = .599$, $p < .05$), and Social support ($\beta = .574$, $p < .05$). Hence, social media and social support were significant i.e. could independently and significantly predicts social adjustment of adolescents with visual impairment in the study. Table 8 showed the measures of social media in relations to social adjustment of adolescents with visual impairment in Ibadan, Oyo State.

Table 9 Measures of social support as a correlate of social adjustment of adolescents with visual impairment

s/n	Social support	SD	D	A	SA	\bar{x}	S.D
1	Students with visual impairment cannot learn in the same environment	5 7.1%	9 12.9%	55 78.6%	1 1.4%	2.74	0.606
2	Visual impaired students get bullied in school	9 12.9%	42 60.0%	15 21.4%	4 5.7%	2.20	0.734
3	A shy learner who is blind easily misses a great deal of incidental benefits that come from ordinary school life	14 20.0%	16 22.9%	32 45.7%	8 11.4%	2.49	0.944
4	Due to their impairment students with visual impairment cannot cope with the social adjustment within their environment	16 22.9%	21 30.0%	26 37.1%	7 10.0%	2.34	0.946
5	Lack of social awareness may hinder student performance	12 17.1%	17 24.3%	37 52.9%	4 5.7%	2.47	0.847
6	Students with visual impairment finds it difficult to learn incidentally from their environment	11 15.7%	37 52.9%	17 24.3%	5 7.1%	2.23	0.802
7	Social support if not properly given can affect the social emotion of students	9 12.9%	19 27.1%	34 48.6%	8 11.4%	2.59	0.860
8	My friends could push me into doing just about anything	13 18.6%	18 25.7%	32 45.7%	7 10.0%	2.47	0.912
9	Attitude of teachers of	8	22	36	4	2.51	0.775

	visual impaired students have a lot to do with their academic performance	11.4%	31.4%	51.4%	5.7%		
10	Visual impaired students are usually neglected within the environment	7	17	43	3	2.60	0.730
		10.0%	24.3%	61.4%	4.3%		

Weighted Mean= 2.46

Table 9 showed the measures of social support in relations to social adjustment of adolescents with visual impairment in Ibadan, Oyo State.

Table 10 Measure of social adjustment of adolescents with visual impairment

s/n	Social Adjustment	SD	D	A	SA	\bar{x}	S.D
1	Visual impaired student should also be allowed to access social media as their sighted counterparts	1	44	15	10	2.49	0.756
		1.4%	62.9%	21.4%	14.3%		
2	Attitude of teachers of visual impaired student have a lot to do with their academic performance	7	8	26	29	3.10	0.965
		10.0%	11.4%	37.1%	41.4%		
3	You feel life is dull and uninteresting	11	18	37	4	2.49	0.83
		15.7%	25.7%	52.9%	5.7%		
4	You feel your parent should allow you more freedom	8	34	22	6	2.37	0.802
		11.4%	48.6%	31.4%	8.6%		
5	You get discourage easily	9	23	28	10	2.56	0.895
		12.9%	32.9%	40.0%	14.3%		
6	You think your classmate do not get along with	8	26	27	9	2.53	0.863
		11.4%	37.1%	38.6%	12.9%		
7	You feel that is full of difficulties and problems	6	25	36	3	2.51	0.717
		8.6%	35.7%	51.4%	4.3%		

Weighted Mean= 2.58

Table 10 showed the measures of social adjustment of adolescents with visual impairment in Ibadan, Oyo State.

Discussion

From the findings, it was shown that social media and social support enhanced social adjustment of adolescents with visual impairment in the study. The level at which an adolescent with visual impairment adjust n the community depends on the level at which they are viewed in the society, this enables them perform better and more effectively , among the things that can enable them to

achieve this is the parental influence of which such adolescent with visual impairment it starts from the home since it is the first school of the child before adolescent gets out to mingle with peers and friends, this was in line with the view of Crounter and Head (2002) argued about that parental monitoring and support are correlated highly with post adjustment.

This implies that the joint contribution of the independent variables to the dependent variable was significant and that other variables not included in this model may have accounted for the remaining variance. This is in line with Celeste (2006), Macgaha and Farran(2001) who reported that the visual impaired spend time alone in a solitary and parallel place and do not usually engaged imaginative play or social interaction with their sighted mates and this may be due to the limitation they face in perceiving both visual cues and with this there is nonverbal movement that may present poor social skills than their sighted mates and this may result in social isolation this is where support is needed ti adjust and cope with academic and societal life,

The study also shows the relative contribution of the independent variable [social media and social support] to the dependent variable [social adjustment] of adolescent with visual impairment. This is justified by Pavri and Monda-amaya 2009 which states that human need to interact this is the period an adolescent interacts more and need to be supported socially in other not to interact with those that can influences them negatively

Conclusion

Support factor have a joint significant contribution on adjustment of persons with visual impairment. The need for improved adjustment of adolescents with visual impairment is therefore becoming imperative and it depends on many factors such as level of education, economic status of the parents, family and social support, attitude of members of the society access to information and health facilities, the victim's well being, school support, support of religious people, community support and instrumental support.

Recommendation

This paper therefore recommends that:

- All concerned stakeholders in the affairs of adolescents with visual impairment should ensure that, adolescents with visual impairment received much attention from so as to give room for the improved social adjustment
- Adolescents with visual impairment should be exposed to social media groups which will help in giving them sense of belonging and afford them the opportunity to relate with other peers in the society
- It should be noted that, adolescence is a crucial stage that needs to be handled with care, so as a parent, guidance and family of adolescents with

visual impairment, there should be a close contact with this set of people so as to incorporate good norms, values and necessary skills that will help their social adjustment.

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